

PRODUCTION AND ASSESSMENT OF *JATROPHA CURCAS* OIL BASED BIOLUBRICANT FOR LIGHT GEAR APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

The *jatropha curcas* oil was extracted from the seed with the use of a soxhlet apparatus with petroleum ether as the solvent for oil extraction. The extracted oil was subjected to physiochemical characterisation to determine its density, acid value, free fatty acid value (FFA) content, kinematic viscosity at 50 °C and 100 °C, its viscosity index and saponification value. A value of 15.2% was determined for the FFA which is above the threshold value for oils to be used as lubricant thus indicating that virgin *Jatropha curcas* seed oil is unsuitable for use as lubricant in its raw form. Thus the raw, unaltered *jatropha curcas* oil was pre-treated via esterification using methanol and this reduced the FFA content to 0.51%. This pre-treated oil with lower FFA was then subjected to a two stage transesterification process. The first stage saw the oil transformed into its methyl esters (FAME) and the second stage transforming the methyl ester through polyol transesterification with ethylene glycol resulting in the synthesis of the biolubricant. The synthesised biolubricant was assessed for conformance with current industrial standard lubricant and its tribological and thermal properties were in line. The biolubricant had pour point, kinematic viscosity at 50 °C and 100 °C, and viscosity index determined to be -8 °C, 59.25cSt, 11.52cSt and 191.15 respectively. These values showed that the formulated biolubricant exhibits favourable properties even at low temperature, stable viscosity-temperature behaviour, and perfect lubricative properties. These performance parameters were found to be in tandem with ISO VG-46 commercial lubricants which are utilised in light and industrial gear applications.

Keywords: *Jatropha curcas*, biolubricant, two stage transesterification, tribological and thermal properties, oil extraction, physiochemical characterisation

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1. INTRODUCTION

The demand for petroleum-based lubricants has put a strain on the world reserve of crude oil. It has also been discovered that there are negative environmental consequences associated with

the use of petroleum-based lubricants (Adolf et al., 2018), (Udounwa and Wilson, 2025). These reasons and more have necessitated the need for a deviation from the use of petroleum-based products to the use of more environmentally friendly alternatives. The use of “green” lubricants has been envisaged. This is due to the fact that they are readily available and most importantly, they are biodegradable, thus rendering them environmentally friendly (Wilson et al., 2024). A drawback to the use of green alternatives is that it puts a strain on the availability of food for human consumption. To this end, it has been suggested that only parts of plants which are not edible be used as bio-lubricants (Karmakar et al., 2017). This has assisted in freeing up large volumes of agricultural products for human usage and consumption. This also serves as a means of recycling agricultural waste. *Jatropha curcas* seed is known for its possession of high oil yield and due to its inedible nature, it serves as an excellent alternative for use as bio-lubricant (Li and Wang, 2015). On its own, raw *Jatropha curcas* seed oil has poor oxidative stability, high pour point, and an inadequate viscosity index, and these factors render it unsuitable for use as lubricant. To remedy this disadvantage, the raw *Jatropha curcas* oil must be subjected to chemical modifications such as transesterification, epoxidation, and polyesterification, which would transform it and render it suitable for use as bio-lubricant. This research looks at the synthesis of bio-lubricant from *Jatropha curcas* seed oil and assessing its suitability for use in industries by comparing it side-by-side with ASTM standard performing lubricants (Musa et al., 2016).

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials and reagents

The materials used for this study include *Jatropha curcas* seed, analytical grade reagents used include petroleum ether, potassium hydroxide (KOH), sodium hydroxide (NaOH), hydrochloric acid (HCl), sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄), isopropyl alcohol, sodium methoxide solution, and phenolphthalein indicator. All chemicals were procured in high quality to minimize experimental variability.

2.2 Instruments and equipment

The following instruments were used, a mechanical press for pulverizing the seeds to reduce diameter and increase the surface area for the extraction solvent to penetrate, a soxhlet apparatus for extraction of oil from pulverized seeds, a viscometer for measuring the resulting oils viscosity. Other equipment include a heating mantle, water bath, an analytical weighing balance, laboratory glassware including graduated cylinders, conical flasks, burettes, pipettes, beakers, round bottom flasks were procured and employed. Magnetic stirrers, retort stands with clamps, Liebig condensers with ground glass joints, thermometers were used in measuring room and elevated temperatures.

2.3 Methodological approach

The methodology for this study was achieved in the following phases.

- i. Preliminary preparation of *Jatropha curcas* seed parts prior to oil extraction.
- ii. Extraction of oil from pulverized and dried *Jatropha curcas* seed.
- iii. Physicochemical characterization of extracted *Jatropha curcas* oil.

- iv. Chemical modification of extracted *Jatropha curcas* oil via esterification and transesterification to produce the biolubricant.
- v. Testing and comparison of produced biolubricant with ASTM standard lubricants.

2.3.1 Preliminary Preparation of *Jatropha curcas* Seed before extraction (Oil seed pre-treatment)

The following processes were undertaken when preparing the specimens prior to extraction. These processes included:

a) Washing of Seed Parts

Here, the avocado seed parts were washed in water to remove debris. This was done so as to avoid contamination of the oil during extraction.

b) Pulverisation of seed

The seeds were grated, that is, reduced in size to allow for increased surface area so the solvent that is used can percolate and get to every area and part of the substrates. As shown in Figures 1a-b is a pictorial representation of the grating process.

Fig 1a and 1b: Pulverisation of *Jatropha* seeds to increase the surface area prior to oil extraction

c) Drying of Pulverised *Jatropha* Seed to remove moisture

The Pulverised Seeds (see Figure 2) were spread under the sun for four (4) days to achieve perfect dryness. They were dried to remove all forms of moisture prior to extraction. The figure below shows the avocado parts while being dried.

Fig. 2: Pulverised grated *Jatropha* seeds

2.3.2 Extraction of oil from pulverized and dried *Jatropha curcas* seed.

As shown in Figure 3, the oil extraction was carried out at the pharmacognosy postgraduate laboratory, University of Uyo, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. The solvent extraction method was selected due to its efficiency in terms of oil yield. Since oil is a non-polar material, a non-polar solvent was selected to be used for the extraction. Petroleum Ether was used in extracting oils from the specimens. The Soxhlet extraction method was used in a bid to minimize solvent loss and maximise its use.

2000g of dried in batches of 500g, crushed and dried *Jatropha* seeds were put into the extraction chamber. Petroleum Ether was put into the boiling flask. And the set up was clamped onto the heating mantel. The heating mantel was switched on and temperature was maintained at 10 °C. As the heating mantel temperature increased, the Petroleum Ether evaporated from temperature increase. Upon evaporation, it flowed into the condenser section where water supply cooled it off and it dropped into the extraction chamber.

When the condensed petroleum ether filled the extraction chamber, it was siphoned back into the boiling flask together with the extracted oil from the extraction chamber.

This process was repeated for four (4) hours. After that, the equipment was switched off and the crushed seed from which oil was extracted into the solvent was removed and replaced with another 1000g of dried, crushed substrate. After extracting oil from 2000g of crushed and dried *jatropha* seeds, the oil which is fussed with Petroleum Ether inside the boiling flask was poured into a container and kept in the open within room temperature for the petroleum ether to be evaporated thereby remaining only pure avocado seed.

Fig 3 (a) Weighing the dried, pulverised *Jatropha curcas* seeds (b) Petroleum Ether (c) Heating Mantel (d) Soxhlet apparatus set-up.

2.3.3 CHARACTERIZATION OF JATROPHA CRUDE OIL

Density

Analytical weighing balance was used to weigh an empty beaker, after which its mass was recorded. 40 cm³ of the substrate, which is the *Jatropha curcas* oil was put in the empty beaker, and the new mass was weighed. The net mass of the substrate, which is the *Jatropha curcas* oil, was derived by subtracting the combined mass from the mass of the empty beaker. The density of the oil was derived from the ratio of the sample mass to the known volume, which is 40 cm³ as presented in Equation 1.

$$Density = \frac{\text{Sample Weight}}{\text{Sample Volume}} \quad (1)$$

Viscosity

The kinematic viscosity for the *Jatropha curcas* oil sample was derived at 50°C and 100°C, respectively, using a viscometer. A beaker containing the oil was put inside the heating mantle and the temperature was increased, while constantly stirring the oil to achieve uniform heating. The spindle mounted onto the viscometer was immersed in the oil to the calibration mark, which was situated at the middle of the shaft indentation. The spindle rotated up until steady state conditions were achieved, which was shown by the dial reading. The dynamic viscosity of the sample was identified at the final reading and expressed in millipascal-seconds (mPa), in conformance with ASTM D445 guidelines for viscosity measurement.

Saponification value

The saponification value (SV) was determined in line with AOCS guidelines. 2.00g of *Jatropha curcas* oil was weighed and infused into a conical flask. 50 cm³ of 0.5 N ethanolic KOH was added to the flask and the mixture gently stirred, which resulted in total saponification of the triglycerides. The unreacted KOH was titrated against 0.5 N hydrochloric acid using 3 drops of phenolphthalein indicator (Mohammed-Dabo et al., 2012).

The saponification value of the oil samples was then calculated using Equation 2.

$$SAP\ Value = \frac{(\text{Titre Value})(\text{Normality of NaOH})(56.1)}{\text{Sample Weight}} \quad (2)$$

Pour point

The oil was transferred into a test tube suspended in a laboratory refrigerator and cooled until complete solidification was achieved. The solid test tube was removed and allowed to defrost under ambient temperature, after which a thermometer was used to identify the temperature at which the test tube first began to turn molten. This temperature was recorded as the pour point of the oil. This temperature was seen as the lowest temperature at which the oil exhibited the ability to flow under gravity. This was also indicative of the oil's lowest operational temperature

Percentage free fatty acid (%FFA)

To determine the percentage-free fatty acid in a method in line with the American Oil Chemists' Society (AOCS) Official Method Cd 5a-40, 2.00g of *Jatropha curcas* oil was put in a conical flask and its mass was recorded. 20 ml of isopropyl alcohol and 3 drops of phenolphthalein indicator solution was added. The mixture was titrated with 0.1 N potassium hydroxide solution while being stirred. Stirring continued until a pink end point showed for 30 seconds. The free fatty acid content was derived using Equation 3.

$$\%FFA = \frac{(\text{mL of titrant})(\text{Normality of NaOH})(28.2)}{\text{Sample Weight}} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

Acid value

To determine the acid value of the oil in line with the American Oil Chemists' Society (AOCS) Official Method Cd 5a-40, 1.00g of *Jatropha curcas* oil was put in a conical flask, and 25 milliliters of isopropyl alcohol was added alongside 3 drops of phenolphthalein indicator, 0.1N sodium hydroxide was added and the mixture stirred until a pink precipitate was noticed. The acid value was determined using Equation 4.

$$\text{Acid Value} = \frac{(\text{Titra Value})(\text{Normality of NaOH})(56.1)}{\text{Sample Weight}} \times 100 \quad (4)$$

Oil esterification

Esterification of the oil was necessary to reduce the pre-fatty acid content of the oil. To do this, 100 grams of *Jatropha curcas* oil was put into a 2L round-bottom flask. Methanol and concentrated sulfuric acid of 5% (w/w) and 20% (w/w) respectively were put into a conical flask and poured into the round-bottom flask containing 100 grams of oil. The new mixture was precipitated in a thermostatic water base at 50°C. The reaction was maintained at 50°C under continuous stirring at 500 revolutions per minute (rpm). After an hour (60 minutes), the sample was removed using a pipette and titrated with 0.1N KOH solution. This was done to determine the residual pre-fatty acid content.

2.3.4 Transesterification of the oil

This process converts the triglycerides into fatty acid acyl esters, FAAE, using low molecular weight alcohols such as methanol (Demirbas, 2011). The synthesis of the biolubricant pertaining to this research was achieved through a two-stage transesterification process. This two-stage transesterification process involved:

- (i) The conversion of the extracted oil to methyl esters.
- (ii) Transforming the methyl esters into a polyester through another transesterification reaction involving polyol.

This two-stage transesterification process was chosen as it will result in the synthesis of lubricants with favorable tribological properties, biodegradability, and lubricity.

- (i) **Methyl ester synthesis**

The first stage of transesterification was done using methanol in the presence of potassium hydroxide. 100 milliliters of *Jatropha curcas* oil was reacted with methanol in the ratio 3 to 1 at temperature of 60 degrees centigrade while continuously being steered for a period of 20 minutes.

(ii) Biolubricant synthesis

The second transesterification stage involved the conversion of the methyl ester to biolubricant by reacting it with ethylene glycol in the ratio of 3.5:1. This reaction was carried out in 50 mL batches. 0.5 M sodium methoxide of 0.8% was used and it was prepared by dissolving freshly caught metallic sodium in 20% methanol as the catalyst. The entire reaction lasted for three hours and the mixture was heated to a temperature of 120°C. The process is demonstrated in Figures 4-6.

Fig 4a

Fig 4b

Fig 4c

Fig 4 (a) *Jatropha curcas* oil in a reactor inside water bath (b) preheating of the water bath (c) *Jatropha curcas* oil esterification products in separation funnels

Fig 5a

Fig 5b

Fig 5c

Fig 5(a) Separation of synthesised *Jatropha curcas* oil biolubricant from by-products (b) Cleaning of biolubricant (c) Completely cleaned and separated *Jatropha curcas* oil biolubricant and water

Fig 6: Synthesised *Jatropha curcas* biolubricant in test tubes ready for testing in mechanical industrial applications

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results obtained from the experimental analysis of both the freshly extracted, unaltered *Jatropha curcas* oil and the formulated biolubricant are displayed in Tables 1, 2, and 3. The findings are discussed under three major sub-sections: (i) physicochemical characterization of the crude *Jatropha* oil, (ii) reduction of free fatty acid (FFA) content through esterification, and (iii) evaluation of the physicochemical and lubricating properties of the synthesized *Jatropha*-based biolubricant.

3.1 Characterization of *Jatropha curcas* raw, virgin and unaltered oil

The important characteristics of the crude *Jatropha curcas* oil with reference to lubricity include kinematic viscosities at 50 °C and 100 °C, viscosity index, and pour point. As displayed in Table 1, these characteristics were analysed to be 71.24 cSt, 15.15 cSt, 215.9, and 5 °C, respectively. The combination of relatively high viscosity, excellent viscosity index, and a good pour point are indicative that raw, virgin *Jatropha curcas* oil possesses favourable physicochemical characteristics, making it a suitable and reliable raw material for biolubricant productions. The esterification result showing the decrease in FFA with time is presented in Table 2. Furthermore, the properties of synthesized biolubricant are shown in Table 3.

Table 1: Characteristics of *Jatropha curcas* Oil

S/N	Property	Units	Values
1	Density	Kg/m	910.7
2	Acid value	Mg KOH/g	31.07
3	Free fatty acid(FFA)	%	13.9
4	Saponification value	-	189.94
5	Pour point	°C	4.7
6	Viscosity@40°C	cSt	71.24
7	Viscosity@100°C	cSt	15.15
8	Viscosity index (vi)	-	215.9

Table 2: The esterification result showing the decrease in FFA with time.

S/N	Time (h)	FFA (%)
1	0	15.2
2	1	13.25
3	2	6.98
4	3	4.32
5	4	2.15
6	5	0.51

Table 3. Properties of synthesized biolubricant alongside standard properties according to ISO VG-46 and those of petroleum based lubricant (Abdullahi ,2012)

Property	<i>Jatropha</i> crude oil	<i>Jatropha</i> biolubricant	ISO VG-46	Petroleum based lubricant*
Density @ 25°C (Kg/m) ³	910.7	902.8	-	885.6
Viscosity@40°C (cSt)	71.24	59.25	>41.4	10.801
Viscosity@100°C (cSt)	15.15	11.52	>4.1	3.136
Viscosity index	215.9	191.15	>90	165.4
Pour point	5	-8	-10	-9

The free fatty acid (FFA) content of the raw, virgin *Jatropha curcas* oil was analysed to be 15.2%, which is quite high. At this high value, the direct use of the extracted raw *Jatropha curcas* oil for lubricant synthesis would likely result in very high saponification values, leading to undesirable consequences such as foam formation. Also, in alkaline-catalyzed

transesterification, excessive FFA content makes difficult the separation of methyl esters from glycerol, this reduces the overall yield of fatty acid methyl ester (FAME). Several researchers have reported that the FFA level of oils or fats used in alkaline transesterification should not exceed 1% (equivalent to 2 mg KOH/g triglyceride) (Freedman et al., 1984; Mittelbach et al., 1994). Values above 1% aid saponification, which not only prevents glycerol–ester separation but also reduces the transformation rate and yield of FAME, which is also called biodiesel. Ho et al., (2020) further approved that an acidity level below 1.00 mg KOH/g triglyceride (approximately 0.5% FFA) is ideal for efficient biodiesel production. In the light of this, the high FFA value of the raw *Jatropha curcas* oil necessitated pre-treatment. As shown in Table 2, this was effectively reduced to below 1% through esterification with methanol, this act rendered the oil suitable for subsequent transesterification and biolubricant production.

3.2 FFA Reduction by esterification

The progressive reduction of free fatty acid (FFA) content with time, monitored at one-hour intervals, is presented in Table 2. The initial FFA value of 15.2% was effectively reduced by the esterification of the raw oil with methanol. This pretreatment step was essential, as El-Diwani et al. (2010) reported that oils with FFA values greater than 1% negatively impact the efficiency of the transesterification reaction. In such cases, FFAs readily synthesize with the alkaline catalyst to form soaps, this process referred to as saponification, which lowers the availability of catalyst for ester formation. Soap formation also supports emulsion, and this results in lowering biodiesel yield and complicating downstream separation and purification processes (Emin, 2008). To avoid these issues and encourage an efficient methyl ester reaction, the esterification reaction was conducted until a significant reduction in FFA was noticed. After five hours of reaction, the FFA level was successfully reduced to 0.51%, as shown in Table 2, which falls well within the recommended threshold for subsequent transesterification.

3.3 Analysis of produced *Jatropha* biolubricant

The synthesized *Jatropha curcas* biolubricant was subjected to key physicochemical and lubricity tests in order to evaluate its suitability as a base stock for lubricating oil applications. The properties analyzed included pour point, kinematic viscosities at 50 °C and 100 °C, and viscosity index. The results are presented in Table 3, alongside those of the raw, virgin, unaltered *Jatropha* oil, ISO VG 46 standards for light gear applications, and petroleum-based lubricants as reported by Abdullahi (2012). ISO VG 46 is one of the most widely consumed viscosity grades in the world, accounting for more than 70% of lubricant usage (Ghazi et al., 2010). Kinematic viscosities at 50 °C and 100 °C are important indicators of excellent flow properties and thermal stability, as they are indicative of lubricant performance at low and high temperatures. The viscosities of the produced *Jatropha* biolubricant were a little lower than those of the raw, unaltered *Jatropha curcas* oil but fell within the acceptable range specified by ISO VG 46 (Table 3). The viscosity index of the produced biolubricant was determined to be 191.15, a value comparable to other vegetable oil based (green) biolubricants. A high viscosity index is a good property of a lubricant, as it shows little variation in viscosity with temperature changes and shows stable lubricity under wide-ranging operating conditions. The pour point, defined as the least temperature at which an oil is able to flow under prescribed conditions, is a very important property for lubricants to be used in low-temperature conditions. The pour point of the *Jatropha* biolubricant improved significantly from 5 °C in the crude oil to –8 °C after the transesterification reactions. This improvement not only increases the use of the oil under cold conditions but also is in tandem with values reported for other vegetable oil based biolubricants (Ghazi et al., 2010). Also, a slight reduction in density was noticed in the

produced biolubricant in comparison with the raw, unaltered *Jatropha curcas* oil. This reduction can be attributed to the esterification and transesterification processes. This is because these processes changed the molecular structure of the triglycerides. The lower density which came as a result of these modification reactions is good, as it enhances lubricant flow properties and contributes to improved tribological performance. Overall, the produced *Jatropha*-based biolubricant show characteristics almost tandem to ISO VG 46 standards and petroleum based lubricants, showing its potential as a recyclable, biodegradable and environmentally sustainable alternative.

4. CONCLUSION

This study demonstrated that *Jatropha curcas* oil, though unsuitable in its raw state due to high free fatty acid content, can be effectively transformed into a high-performing biolubricant through esterification and two-stage transesterification. The resulting product showed excellent viscosity stability, low pour point, and overall tribological performance comparable to ISO VG-46 standards and petroleum-based lubricants. Beyond meeting technical requirements, the use of *Jatropha* which is a non-edible, renewable feedstock positions this biolubricant as a sustainable alternative that reduces reliance on petroleum while minimizing environmental impact. In essence, this study confirms the potential of *Jatropha*-based lubricants for light gear applications, combining performance with ecological responsibility.

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